

INTERNATIONAL TERRORISM, ELECTRONIC MEDIA-OPERATION AND REGULATION OF TV NEWS CHANNELS DURING THE TERRORISM COVERAGE

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ABSTRACT

The concept of globalization or internationalization of certain wars, which were result of terrorist activities worldwide, as well as the high attention of terrorism coverage worldwide broadcasting might open up better opportunities to journalists – particularly to those who work in democratic countries like U.S.A and India – to improve their coverage. The context is the key: the context of the operation methodology, follow of regulatory bodies guidelines, the journalistic culture and the global environment.

It is very important how media presents consequences of terrorist acts, how information is transmitted to public. Television and press have had a significant impact on how public receives terrorist acts and their consequences. As a result, nearly each public survey indicates that responders almost anywhere put fear of terrorist acts on the top of their priority list.

In order to reach out a conclusion on this paper, a researcher has gone through number of books related to terrorism and media, has examined significant number of journals which deals with core issue of terrorism and its coverage by media.

Key words: terrorism, BBC, CNN, CNN-IBN, coverage, regulation

For citation:

Dwivedi, R., Partlow, L. & Bute, S. (2017). International Terrorism, Electronic Media-Operation and Regulation of TV News Channels During the Terrorism Coverage. *Psycholinguistics*, 22 (1), 70–91.

Introduction

For most of the television age, from the end of World War II to the collapse of the Soviet Union, the deployment of positive and negative political labels was an integral part of Cold War politics and its dualistic view of the world. «Terrorism» was used extensively to characterize enemies of the United States and its allies, as in President Reagan’s assertion in 1985, that Libya, Cuba, Nicaragua and North Korea constituted a «confederation of terrorist states» intent on undermining American attempts «to bring stable and democratic government» to the developing world. Conversely, «friendly» states, like Argentina, could wage a full scale internal war against «terrorism», using a definition elastic enough to embrace almost anyone who criticized the regime or held unacceptable opinions, and attract comparatively little censure despite the fact that this wholesale use of state terror killed and maimed many more civilians than the more publicized incidents of «retail» terror-assassinations, kidnappings and bombings.

Using modern means terrorism learned how to apply opportunities provided by media. Terrorists are able to exploit all advantages of media using them for presenting their political objectives and for gaining the support of the Islam world. In our opinion media multiply the impact of terrorist attacks. Global communications means provide real time coverage on terrorist acts. Each and every terrorist attack is a piece of news in the world. That is why it is not only the fact of destruction which is important for terrorists but also its social-psychological impact. Unexpected terrorist attacks are followed by panic, confusion among people which is news for media. For terrorist organisations «after action publicity» plays a very important role in their acknowledgement to which media are key. Freedom of press is a democratic achievement. In some cases this assists terrorists because media can increase uncertainty and fear among people.

Terrorist organisations and terrorist select their targets carefully and the murdered victims or destroyed facilities comprise terrorists' messages to public and media. This message is used for intimidation, generating fear, transmitting terrorists' demands. It is well known that media will report on terrorist acts and show the bloodiest pictures without delay.

It took 9/11 to truly give it a global dimension. Problem is no nearer to a solution. The temptation to add «before it gets worse» has to be avoided. It is not likely to get better for a long time to come. The role of media in covering terrorism was dramatically high lightened in the aftermath of September 11 bombings in west and 26/11 in India. Perhaps for the first time ever the primacy of Anglo-American media channels CNN and BBC was challenged by a Qatar based Arabic station Al-Jazeera to challenge the realm of CNN- and BBC. CNN had become the most powerful medium to communicate information, disinformation and misinformation. The National Security advisor Condoleza Rice even suggested to the network to reconsider relying the prerecorded tapes- propaganda tapes- according to her – broadcast via Al-Jazzera. Going live and unedited has been perhaps the greatest challenge to broadcast journalism since the advent of satellite broadcast.

Similarly in India 26/11 put forward many challenges and raised many questions on the methodologies adopted by TV Channels to cover and portray it on screen about terror act.

The coverage of movement of marine commandos by Hindi and English both TV channels which alerted the operators were highly criticized by media experts. The 24 *7 channels broadcasted live on operation and gave minute details about the whole operation to their viewers which resulted broadcasters association in India to issue certain guidelines for TV channels. The insurgency in Jammu and Kashmir and random operation of security forces also get coverage on TV channels which some time crosses the set boundaries by TV channels.

Same happens when major or minor terror acts take place across India and TV channels loses their patience in order to get 'breaking' not realizing the sensitivity of issue.

1.1. Objective and Aim of Paper. «Terrorism» is a term that cannot be given a stable definition. Or rather, it can, but to do so forestalls any attempt to examine the major feature of its relation to television in the contemporary world. As the central public arena for organizing ways of picturing and talking about social and political life, TV plays a pivotal role in the contest between competing definitions, accounts and explanations of terrorism.

The objective of research is divided in five major areas where I intend to focus. First is to understand the term terrorism and broadcast media separately. Secondly to establish a relation between the terrorism and its coverage on medium. The study is focused on how the coverage of international terrorism has been so far on international and domestic media. Fourth stage is to study about the regulatory bodies on their guidelines to broadcast medium on coverage of terrorism. The study has carried a detail about how media channels has portrayed the issue of terrorism and where they have crossed the set guidelines. The last stage has carried a detail guideline and study on what needs to be done within regulatory bodies and broadcast medium to act upon while covering the issue of terrorism.

- To understand the term «International Terrorism» in broader perspective.

- To know «The Medium-Electronic Media». It is first necessary to define the terms used in the title of this article.

Media is a generic term meaning all the methods or channels of information and entertainment. The mass media are taken to encompass newspapers, radio and television, but other important forms of communications include books, films, music, theatre and the visual arts. The late twentieth century has seen the globalisation of the mass media culture, but we should not overlook the fact that throughout history informal methods of communication such as the gossip of the taverns, streets and marketplaces have been the standard local media for transmitting information, and these informal channels coexist with all the latest multimedia technology in contemporary societies.

- To carry out a detail study on how the coverage of issue of terrorism is portrayed on Electronic Medium. **Critical study of Channels on their response to coverage of terrorism of selected events like 9/11 and 26/11 consequences of them.**

- An analytical study of regulatory bodies and guidelines proposed by them for broadcast journalists.
- To put forward a comprehensive conclusion on what needs to be done by regulatory bodies, broadcast medium and broadcast journalists while covering the issue of terrorism and a study on what they have done so far.

1.2-Research Question and Issues for Discussion

Hence the research question in this paper is basically circling around.

1.2.1-Definition of Terrorism – Remember there are two philosophy on it. One which has been defined by U.S.A administration which randomly comes across scrutiny. Similary International media questions the Indian govt's definition of terrorism in certain parts mostly in case of J&K. There is other side of definition which is suggested by media critic and social activist. This is discussed.

The term terrorism as used in this paper denotes a particular type of violence. It is not employed as a synonym for politically motivated violence in general. It has five distinguishing characteristics:

1. it is premeditated and designed to create a climate of extreme fear;
2. it is directed at a wider target than the immediate victims;
3. it inherently involves attacks on random or symbolic targets, including civilians;
4. it is considered by the society in which it occurs as «extra-normal», that is in the literal sense that it violates the norms regulating disputes, Protest and dissent; and it is used primarily, though not exclusively, to influence the political behaviour of governments, communities or specific social groups. The weapon of terror is used extensively by both sub-state and state actors in the international system, and has, since the 1980s, been increasingly used by groups with a religious motivation and as a method of intimidating the authorities or media.

1.2.2 – Coverage by Broadcast Media. The basic question which is raised by researcher is the role of media in covering the issue of terrorism. It deals with not realizing the sensitivity of issue. Sharing the platform with govt as mouth piece of govt as has been

questioned by media critics in case of BBC and CNN. The paper is analyzing the coverage of these four channels and portrayal of terrorism by analyzing the text of script, the video footage and having discussion with key reporters. A verbal permission has been granted by a senior editorial staff of CNN-IBN. The researcher is aspiring to study the discussions and reports of **selected terrorism events like 9/11 and 26/11**.

In order to achieve their objectives terrorist organisations need all forms of mass media. It is very important how media presents consequences of terrorist acts, how information is transmitted to public. Previously terrorist acts had less attention than nowadays. It is worth to see that terrorist attacks in New York, Madrid, London or Bali had record publicity in mass media while terrorist acts committed in other regions had only «standard» coverage. Television and press have had a significant impact on how public receives terrorist acts and their consequences. As a result, nearly each public survey indicates that responders almost anywhere put fear of terrorist acts o the top of their priority list.

Information (comments) attached to news on terrorist acts have a large influence on the views and responses of public, particularly when the event is met with wide consensus (condemnation) and no exchange of opinions is possible. In such cases different opinions do not clash and there is no debate over the consideration of terrorist acts. In other words deliberate distortion remains invisible. Characteristic features of terrorist acts, suicide attacks can be summarised in one remarkable fact: terrorist acts are committed for the public and for influencing the public. Without either of these terrorism – from a terrorist aspect – is useless and pointless. One of the important intentions of terrorists is escalation: to advertise their views, to make their objectives accepted, to increase the number of their supporters, to enhance the efficiency of their actions. All these are impossible to achieve without sufficient publicity to their actions. This is also well known by their enemies but the brutality of actions forces media to provide news coverage or even detailed accounts. Therefore terrorist attacks appear to be propaganda actions aimed at making certain doctrines or views popular through the use of modern means of mass media. Terrorist acts are usually bloody dramas tailored to the needs

of media by a terrorist that is terrorists try to achieve as large an input as possible. After all no secret action of some selected few is not intended to remain in secret during their execution.

1.2.3 – Role of regulatory bodies. Regulatory bodies are supposed to issue some fundamental guidelines to broadcast media and media persons when they cover and report on terrorism. But the question is how far they have practiced their duties? The study has analyzed the existing guidelines proposed by these regulatory bodies and their methods to ensure the action by media channels. And if no, then why it has not been influential in pressurizing the media channels to follow the set guidelines?

A policy option on media response to terrorism is some form of media censorship or statutory regulation. In view of the great power wielded by-the media, for good or ill, it is hardly surprising to find that, when faced with severe terrorist campaigns, several democratic countries have sought to deny the terrorist direct access to the important platform of the broadcast media. This was clearly the prime concern underlying former Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher's demand that the terrorists should be starved of the oxygen of publicity, and the British government's ban, since rescinded, on broadcasting the voices of terrorist spokespersons.

1.2.4 – Recommendations of Research. The researcher has analyzed all the situation at national and international level which contains wide definition of terrorism, coverage by broadcast media, role of regulatory bodies and then has proposed a study based on research and existing guidelines, which may suggest broadcast media on their principles and guidelines while covering the issue of terrorism. There are a number of other important ways in which responsible media in a democracy serve to frustrate the aims of terrorists.

Terrorists like to Present themselves as noble Robin Hoods, champions of the oppressed and downtrodden. By showing the savage cruelty of terrorists' violence and the way in which they violate the rights of the innocent, the media can help to shatter this myth. It is quite easy to show, by plain photographic evidence, how terrorists have failed to observe any laws or rules of war, how they have murdered women and children, the old and the sick, without

compunction. For in terrorist practice no one is innocent, no one can be neutral, for all are potentially expendable for the transcendental ends of terrorist cause.

What else can the media do in a positive way to aid in the struggle against terrorism? There are numerous practical forms of help they can provide. Responsible and accurate reporting of incidents can create heightened vigilance among the public to observe, for example, unusual packages, suspicious persons or behaviour. At the practical level the media can carry warnings to the public from the police, and instructions as to how they should react to an emergency. Frequently media with international coverage can provide valuable data and leads concerning foreign movements, links between personalities and different terrorist personalities and different terrorist organisations, new types of weaponry and possible future threats, such as the planning of an international terrorist 'spectacular', or warning signs of a new threat. Finally, the media also provide an indispensable forum for informed discussion concerning the social and political implications of terrorism and the development of adequate policies and counter-measures. And media which place a high value on democratic freedoms will, rightly and necessarily, continually remind the authorities of their broader responsibilities to ensure that the response to terrorism is consistent with the rule of law, respect for basic rights and the demands of social justice. In sum, it can be argued that these contributions by the media to the war against terrorism are so valuable that they outweigh the disadvantages and risks and the undoubted damage caused by a small minority of irresponsible journalists and broadcasters. The positive work of the media has been either gravely underestimated or ignored. It is always fair game, especially for politicians, to attack the media. A more considered assessment suggests that the media in western liberal states are a weapon that can be used as a major tool in the defeat of terrorism. The media need not become the instrument of the terrorist.

Hence researcher put forward the topic «International Terrorism and Electronic Media—Operation and Regulation of Electronic Media during Terrorism Coverage» in order to reach on **Decision-Making**.

The basic questions which are arising in proposed paper are – Do we really understand the term Terrorism?

- a) Do we find that the term terrorism has been used by some nation to widely categories a particular ethnic race or religion for their own glory and power?
- b) How fit and true are the western definitions or definition given in developing world?
- c) How far broadcast media has played its role on defining the term and creating awareness about the term «International Terrorism»?
- d) How responsible international and national media(Study of BBC,CNN,CNN-IBN and Aaj Tak) have been in portraying news, live coverage, discussions and talk shows related to terrorism?
- e) Have these channels portrayed and thus created awareness among viewers about terrorism?
- f) Have they followed existing guidelines proposed by concerned regulatory bodies and have adopted a restrained methodology while dealing with the issue of terrorism?
- g) Have the channels not glorified the term terrorism?
- h) What are regulatory bodies?
- i) What they have done or what guidelines they have set to suggest broadcast media while covering sensitive issues like terrorism?
- j) How far they have succeeded to pressurize the channels to follow the guidelines?
- k) What are these guidelines?
- l) What are the loopholes in these guidelines?
- m) What is the proposed way in the thesis on principles and guidelines for broadcast media while covering the issue of terrorism?
- n) Why the study required and why the existing guidelines have succeeded or not succeeded?

2.0-International Terrorism and Media in General – To summarise briefly on the symbiotic nature of the relationship between terrorists and the media, the recent history of terrorism in many democratic countries vividly demonstrates that terrorists do thrive on the oxygen of publicity, and it is foolish to deny this. This does not mean that the established democratic media share the values of the terrorists. It does demonstrate, however, that the free media in an open society are particularly vulnerable to exploitation and manipulation by ruthless terrorist organisations. In using TV, radio and the print media the terrorists generally have four main objectives:

- 1) To convey the propaganda of the deed and to create extreme fear among their target group/S;
- 2) To mobilise wider support for their cause among the general population, and international opinion by emphasising such themes as righteousness of their cause and the inevitability of their victory;
- 3) To frustrate and disrupt the response of the government and security forces, for example by suggesting that all their practical antiterrorist measures are inherently tyrannical and counterproductive;
- 4) To mobilise, incite and boost their constituency of actual and potential supporters and in so doing to increase recruitment, raise more funds and inspire further attacks.

3.0-Litreture Review

The researcher has examined and read number of books, journals and magazines in order to design the framework of this paper. Terrorism is a wide issue and can not be given a stable definition. However keeping the opinion of majority of critics, governments and journalists there is conclusion on the definition of terrorism. The definition which is proposed by countries like U.S.A and west has widely been accepted. Also true is the opinion that ethnic identical crisis has forced Islam to act in a way which is widely considered as terrorist activities. Even then there are various shades of terrorism. A particular religion always can not be figured out as a religion of terrorist. There has been other ethnic and religious groups which are involved in terrorist activities and there is a complete list of such groups and organizations.

Similarly media professionals and the media in general have paid a heavy toll to terrorism in recent years. Dozens of journalists in Algeria, the Balkans, Colombia, Spain, the Philippines and elsewhere have been intimidated, kidnapped and assassinated so that they could be silenced.

In order to reach out on a conclusion on this paper, researcher has gone through number of books related to terrorism and media, has examined significant number of journals which deals with core issue of terrorism and its coverage by media, apart from continuous tracking of channels like BBC, CNN, CNN-IBN and Aaj Tak and

website associated with the issue, and then he proposes the above said Ph D proposal.

Apart from books, researcher has also examined previously done researches on this area and found that issue of terrorism has been dealt in many researches but the regulation of media on issue of coverage of terrorism has not been worked upon. Hence researcher proposed the above said study in this paper.

3.1-Purpose of Review – To gain a background knowledge of the research topic.

To identify the concepts relating to it, potential relationships between previous researches and to formulate researchable hypothesis.

To identify appropriate methodology, research design, methods of measuring concepts and techniques of analysis.

To identify data sources used by other researchers.

To learn how others structured their reports.

4.0.-Research Methodology

4.1-Descriptive research – In this paper researcher has done descriptive research by analyzing the status of terrorism in contemporary scenario. Not to say that last twenty years has been the most disastrous years of human civilization. Before the Al Qaeda's lethal attack on world trade centre European and South Asian countries were fighting with domestic terrorism. And so were the challenges before broadcast media Like in case of Britain. Television journalism in Britain has faced a particular problem in reporting «the Irish Question» since the Republican movement has adopted a dual strategy using both the ballot box and the bullet, pursuing its claim for the ultimate reunification of Ireland electorally, through the legal political party, Sinn Fein, and militarily, through the campaign waged by the illegal Irish Republican Army. Added to which, the British state's response has been ambiguous. Ostensibly, as Prime Minister Thatcher argued in 1990, although «hey are at war with us», «we can only fight them with the civil law».

India has also been fighting with its core problem Terrorism since its independence. But most affected years has been after 1980 when Khalistan issue came in picture and then the issue of north east, LTTE and Kashmir insurgency. TV Media has reported on these issues

extensively. Some time with sensitivity and some time it crossed the set boundaries.

The researcher will go in all details while dealing with issue by applying descriptive research methodology.

4.2-Analytical research – Television’s ability to strike the balance is not just a question for news, current affairs and documentary production however. The images and accounts of terrorism offered by television fiction and entertainment are also important in orchestrating the continual contest between the discourse of government and the state, the discourses of legitimated opposition groups, and the discourses of insurgent movements. This struggle is not simply for visibility – to be seen and heard. It is also for credibility – to have one’s views discussed seriously and one’s case examined with care. The communicative weapons in this battle are unevenly distributed however.

News is a relatively closed form of television programming. It privileges the views of spokespeople for governments and state agencies and generally organises stories to converge around officially sanctioned resolutions.

The paper examines all the facts available so far. The details from specific TV Channels will be collected to go thorough the text of coverage of terrorism, discussion on this issue which has been conducted in studios, and examination of footage available in video library of TV channels. On the same pattern guidelines, datas and facts of regulatory bodies will be studied in order to reach out on a conclusion on how they have performed so far.

4.3-Quantitative research – Television in a democratic society requires the greatest possible diversity of open programme forms if it is to address the issues raised by terrorism in the complexity they merit. Whether the emerging forces of technological change, in production and reception, channel proliferation, increased competition for audiences and transnational distribution, will advance or block this ideal is a question well worth examining.

In the proposed research, researcher has examined the acts of terror in major countries specially in India. The data’s are collected from media TV channels, regulatory bodies and govt agencies to analyze the number, places and intensity and loss in these acts of

terror. The study also involves an statistical analysis of operation of specified TV channels while coverage of it. Statistics reveals on what percentage of total coverage was given to terrorism and how the mood of public was examined. It further reveal the change in the mood of news producers while reflecting on terrorism.

4.4-Qualitative research – After 26/11 in India when a group of ten terrorists entered in Mumbai and seized India's financial capital for 59 hrs., a debate started on the role of media. The war against Terror as it was broadcasted on CNN-IBN, which launched a campaign against terror extended in to a form of debate across the country. Different media channels broadcasted it and International Media too came to support the domestic media. Since American and other foreigner were killed in this terror attack and terrorists targeted symbol of India's prosperity, Hotel Taj and Hotel Oberai, henceforth entire event was called India's 9/11 by media channels. And almost like 9/11 International community came in support. America asked Pakistan, where from the terrorist came down, to act on terror. And Pakistan did some exercises on LeT and its front organization Jamat – ud. Dawa. The entire coverage by media channels kept viewers informed about day to day activity.

The September 11 events in the US have been a profound test of the professionalism of journalists worldwide and, apart from the inevitable banalities and some bizarre exceptions, coverage appears to have been restrained, intelligent and informed. However, there have been numerous attempts to manipulate the media message by governments creating undue pressure on journalists that is potentially damaging to the quality of coverage of the conflict.

By applying qualitative research methodology researcher intend to examine the post 9/11 and post 26/11 phenomenon and due coverage of terrorism by TV channels. The study w deals in detail, about the shift in coverage of terrorism and regulations followed by TV channels in this issue. Role of regulatory bodies will also be examined in detail. This methodology helps researcher on studying, how effective and intensified has been the coverage of terrorism after these two major events of terrorism.

4.5-Conceptual research – The US news media, battered for 25 years by declining credibility, appear to have regained respect

among readers and viewers – at least temporarily – after the September 11 terrorist attacks. Since India has a long history of facing terrorist threats and acts, as they are perceived, in Kashmir and other parts of the country, there is a general climate of understanding over the need for counter terrorism in the country, but journalists have joined a wide-ranging coalition of groups that have protested strongly over recent changes to law that threaten Civil liberties.

The National Union of Journalists (India) and the Indian Journalists Union report that by and large, media coverage of attacks on New York and Washington was professional and unbiased although a section of the media did try to focus attention on Islamic fundamentalism presumably with a view to equate the terrorist attacks on the US with terrorism India. However, to many the «global campaign» has begun to appear as a selective and brutal military campaign to secure the global strategic interests of the West, particularly the US and Britain. Media can play a major role in trying to ensure that the focus of the campaign remains on terrorism and diplomatic ways to resolve the problems.

The researcher develops a study and guideline for broadcast media by applying this research methodology which may guide broadcast media while coverage of issue of terrorism. The research is based on current guidelines and regulation by existing organizations. The research also gives a conceptual framework to the issue of terrorism and its coverage by broadcast media.

5.0-Data Analysis and Findings

The researcher analyzes the data from various sources, which includes – Books and Journals

Electronic Databases

Bibliographic Databases

Abstract Databases

Full-Text Databases

Govt. and Industry Reports

Internet

Research Dissertations / Thesis

Reports of Regulatory bodies

Tracking of selected TV channels.

The finding suggests that there is a clear divide of opinion among selected channels on the defining terrorism.

Project for Excellence in Journalism weekly reports shows the number of hours allotted to terrorism coverage on channels like CNN and BBC has remarkably gone up in post 9/11 coverage. Study suggests that post 9/11 coverage and President Bush war on terror have been widely received by viewers of BBC and CNN. The context of the corporation's structure: The BBC is publicly financed and is the UK's most visible medium in the world. BBC World is part of the corporation's commercial arm but benefits from the BBC's high credibility. The BBC's journalistic and ethical standards and the level of independence from government and political parties are unique – and common sense. Even Conservative politicians, who in general want more competition, helped to preserve the BBC's status in the diminishing field of public service broadcasting. The late 1990s brought a moderate deregulation and the duopoly of the BBC and ITV / Channel 4. CNN, once owned privately by Ted Turner and now part of Time Warner, is now only one of several leading news channels in the US, but was the first of its kind. (ref.: Georgina Born, Scott Collins, Jutta Hammann, Lucy Küng-Shankleman, Sidney Pike, Hank Whittemore etc.).

In the case of India terrorism coverage has been widely acknowledged by viewers of CNN-IBN and Aaj Tak.

Post 26/11 discussions have got wide response.

In the exercise of getting exclusive and breaking these channels has overflowed with the news and programs based on the coverage of terrorism.

Regulatory bodies have not been able efficiently to mar this over flooded information, and due to lack of proper guidelines some time wrong information is also displayed on these channels.

Regulatory bodies have set some norms which must be appraised but study suggests that strict guidelines are needed, through which a standard format may be applied universally to portray news and program related to terrorism and so no one can blame about misinformation or glamorization of content.

Study clearly does not contradict with existing guidelines but put forward some suggestions in order to achieve the objective.

Researcher has monitored these four international channels (BBC, CNN-IBN, CNN and Aaj Tak) for almost one decade in order to achieve designated perception.

The option on media policy on terrorism coverage, and the approach most favoured by the more responsible mass media organisations, is voluntary self-restraint to try to avoid the dangers of manipulation and exploitation by terrorist groups. Many major media organisations have adopted guidelines for their staff with the aim of helping to prevent the more obvious pitfalls. For example, CBS News' guidelines commit the organisation to 'thoughtful, conscientious care and restraint' in its coverage of terrorism, avoiding giving 'an excessive platform for the terrorist/kidnapper.. 'no live coverage of the terrorist/kidnapper' (though live on-the-spot reporting by CBS News reporters is not limited thereby), avoiding interference with the authorities' communications (e.g. telephone lines), using expert advisers in hostage situations to help avoid questions or reports that 'might tend to exacerbate the situation', obeying 'all police instructions' (but reporting to their superiors any instructions that seem to be intended to massage or suppress the news) and attempting to achieve such overall balance as to length' that 'the (terrorist) story does not unduly crowd out other important news of the hour/day'.

The above guidelines are for the most part entirely laudable, and, if properly and consistently implemented, they would help to avoid the worst excesses of media coverage of terrorism. However, one needs to bear in mind that many of those who work in mass media organisations appear blissfully unaware of any guidelines on terrorism news coverage. There is very little evidence of necessary briefing and training of editors and journalists in this sensitive area, and no evidence of any serious effort by media organisations to enforce their own guidelines.²² It is governments, frustration over the apparent inadequacy of media self-restraints that leads some to advocate some form of statutory regulation. If the mass media genuinely wish to exercise due care and responsibility in covering the exceedingly sensitive subject of terrorism, in situations where lives may well be at grave risk, they will need to work harder at devising measures of self-restraint that are both appropriate and effective.

This study analyzes the concept of «objectivity» as it applies to the role played by the global satellite television channels CNN and the BBC in covering major news events within and outside the Western World that also includes its operation in India. The literature review and a critical analysis are intended to show how the roles of CNN and the BBC are changing while dealing with issue of coverage of terrorism. Researcher has planned to include BBC, CNN as international representative channels in this paper while he examined CNN-IBN a counterpart arm of CNN and TV 18 in India and India's most prominent hindi channel Aaj Tak. The plan to start the paper with historical research on international terrorism, a brief description and comparison of the structure, history, ownership and finances of the networks, continues with the description of operation of these networks while covering the issue of terrorism with analytical study of dependent and independent variable, highlights the environment and culture among the journalist on the issue of terrorism and their dealing with the guidelines of regulatory bodies, and analyzes the role, image and impact of CNN, BBC, CNN-IBN and Aaj Tak on the public sphere and mobilization, their viewing perception on terrorism related news and programs and then studies the detail in shift while dealing with the issue of coverage of terrorism through the help dependent and independent variables. It refers to everyday practice and the theories of objectivity as a concept and as a journalistic value – and discusses the question of absolute or contextual objectivity. It deals in detail on what has been the methodology of coverage of issue of terrorism which is adopted by these channels and how far they have gone in following the set guidelines by regulatory bodies.

Investigating coverage of terrorism is also a point which is discussed in this paper. The researcher analyzes whether there are more indications of a global perspective, of a nation-oriented view on international terrorism. The paper deals with whether or not the ideas are substantial or oversimplified for the TV news media as it might help shape their approach to covering the world and their reflections on the possibility of restrained journalism on terrorism.

Conclusion

Can the journalism strategy of the BBC and CNN, CNN-IBN and Aaj Tak lead to a type of journalism that shows respect for both

sides of a conflict? Or, does it contribute to, or perhaps even accelerate, the emotions of public as many believe – particularly between Islamic and non non-Islamic West? The concept of globalization or internationalization of certain wars, which were result of terrorist activities worldwide, as well as the high attention of terrorism coverage broadcast worldwide might open up better opportunities to journalists – particularly to those who work in democratic countries like U.S.A and India – to improve their coverage. But obviously, most of them haven't seized this chance or perhaps don't even see it as a chance. The context is the key: the context of the operation methodology, follow of guidelines of regulatory bodies, and of the journalistic culture and of the global environment.

CNN-IBN is a partnership between CNN and network 18 and the issue of coverage of terrorism has been highly appreciable among viewers after 26/11. Channels even runs a ticker on its screen that if viewers have any complain on the content of channels they may complain it on Broadcasting standard authority of India. Even then the 26/11 coverage and discussion on the issue of terrorism have lead a heated debate among critic on methodology adopted while coverage. Aaj Tak is flagship channel of Living media India Ltd, which also runs several other channels and print magazine. This is India's leading hindi news and current affair channel but the 26/11 coverage and there after has raised debate among regulatory bodies about the way of portrayal of terrorism on screen.

The different structure of BBC and CNN is one reason for their different self-perceptions, their ways of reporting, and the way they are changing on the issue of terrorism. The commercial broadcaster CNN was economically successful until Gulf War II for its journalists' fortitude. The BBC, as a consequence of the ongoing discussions on their financing and status and as a result of economic and technological developments, now tends more towards commercialization, e.g. via the global satellite broadcasting-arm BBC World. But, at least, the BBC's environment is still protected, its «public values», as the discussions following the crossfire of the Hutton Inquiry in the wake of the Kelly Scandal 2003/04 show, are a strong backbone. This context helps to preserve and cultivate journalistic values, including utmost of impartiality while covering sensitive issue like terrorism.

The political power of CNN and the BBC is not as great as many journalists and some researchers think it is. The power in its extent is a myth. The CNN, through the «CNN-effect», or a similarly acting broadcaster cannot drive policy and the BBC does not have the power sometimes attributed to it. (ref.: Royce J. Ammon, Eytan Gilboa, Kai Hafez, Thomas Meyer, Piers Robinson).

Sources of Paper – Discussions with colleagues and experts about the problem, its origin and objectives in seeking a solution.

Examination of data and records for possible trends, peculiarities.

Review of similar studies.

Exploratory personal investigation / Observation.

Logical deduction from the existing theory.

Continuity of research.

Intuition and personal experience.

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УДК 81'23

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1087598

**МІЖНАРОДНИЙ ТЕРОРИЗМ,
ЕЛЕКТРОННЕ МЕДІА-СПОСТЕРЕЖЕННЯ
ТА РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ ТЕЛЕВІЗІЙНИХ
КАНАЛІВ ПІД ЧАС ВИСВІТЛЕННЯ ТЕРОРИЗМУ**

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АНОТАЦІЯ

Концепція глобалізації або інтернаціоналізації окремих воєн, що були наслідком терористичної діяльності в усьому світі, а також висока

увага до поширення тероризму в Інтернеті по всьому світу можуть відкрити для журналістів більш широкі можливості, особливо для тих, хто працює в демократичних країнах, таких як США та Індія, щоб покращити їх охоплення. Дуже важливим є той факт, як засоби масової інформації представляють наслідки терористичних актів, як саме інформація надсилається громадськості.

Ми проаналізували всю ситуацію на національному та міжнародному рівнях, яка містить широке визначення терміну «тероризм», його висвітлення ширококовними засобами масової інформації, роль регулюючих органів, а також запропонували дослідження, засноване на вивченні та існуючих керівних принципах, які можуть бути корисними при трансляції в ЗМІ під час розгляду питання тероризму. Існує ряд інших важливих способів, завдяки яким відповідальні засоби масової інформації в демократії допомагають зривати цілі терористів.

Ключові слова: тероризм, BBC, CNN, CNN-IBN, охоплення, регулювання.

Для цитати:

Дживиді Р., Парталуо С., Бут С. Міжнародний тероризм, електронне медіа-спостереження та регулювання телевізійних каналів під час висвітлення тероризму. *Психолінгвістика. Психолінгвістика. Psycholinguistics*. 2017. Вип. 22 (1). С. 70–91 [англ. мовою].

УДК 81'23

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1087598

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ТЕРРОРИЗМ, ЭЛЕКТРОННОЕ МЕДИА-НАБЛЮДЕНИЕ И РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ТЕЛЕВИЗИОННЫХ КАНАЛОВ ВО ВРЕМЯ ОСВЕЩЕНИЯ ТЕРРОРИЗМА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Концепция глобализации или интернационализации отдельных войн, которые были следствием террористической деятельности во всем

мире, а также высокое внимание к распространению терроризма в Интернете по всему миру могут открыть для журналистов более широкие возможности, особенно для тех, кто работает в демократических странах, таких как США и Индия. Очень важным является тот факт, как средства массовой информации представляют последствия террористических актов, как информация направляется общественности.

Мы проанализировали всю ситуацию на национальном и международном уровнях, которая содержит широкое определение термина «терроризм», его освещение широкоэмитальными средствами массовой информации, роль регулирующих органов, а также предложили исследование, основанное на изучении существующих основных принципах, которые могут быть полезными при трансляции в СМИ во время рассмотрения вопроса терроризма. Существует ряд других важных способов, благодаря которым ответственные средства массовой информации в демократии помогают срывать цели террористов.

Ключевые слова: терроризм, BBC, CNN, CNN-IBN, охват, регулирование.

Для цитаты:

Дживиди Р., Паргалу С., Бут С. Международный терроризм, электронное медиа-наблюдение и регулирование телевизионных каналов во время освещения терроризма. *Психолінгвістика. Психолінгвістика. Psycholinguistics*. 2017. Вып. 22 (1). С. 70–91 [на англ. языке].

Подано до редакції 22.09.2017

Прорецензовано 28.09.2017

Прийнято до друку 04.10.2017